

STRENGTHENING SUSTAINABILITY THROUGH PRESERVATION OF INDIGENOUS KNOWLEDGE SYSTEMS

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Abstract

The preservation of indigenous knowledge and safeguarding it for the sustainable development, the traditional local knowledge and the practices of the indigenous local communities are highly important. The knowledge which is orally transmitted across the generations is deeply rooted in the cultural, spiritual and social values of the indigenous communities. It is intrinsically linked to their land, resources and livelihoods, playing a crucial role in the environmental conservation, sustainable resource management and the integrity of the community.

Sustainable development is guaranteed by the invaluable insights and approaches of the native communities which can enhance the modern scientific knowledge. Ancient knowledge system embodies the time-tested strategies for adapting to the environmental changes, managing biodiversity and utilizing the natural resources sustainably. Integrating indigenous communities into sustainable development initiatives can result in more culturally appropriate, environmentally sound and socially equitable outcomes.

But incidentally they are facing increasing threats due to the factors of globalization, modernization, climate change and land deprivation. The loss of the ancient and primitive knowledge not only erodes the cultural heritage and social cohesion but also diminishes the potential for innovative and sustainable solutions to the contemporary challenges.

Therefore, the preservation and revitalization of the most original knowledge systems are critical for achieving sustainable development goal which requires multi-faceted approaches. This paper discusses about the need and the steps required for the preservation of the Indian knowledge systems so that the goals of sustainable development are achieved.

Keywords: *Indigenous Knowledge, Sustainable Development, Preservation of Cultural Heritage.*

INTRODUCTION: - Sustainable development is a concept that is defined as fulfilling the requirement of the present without depriving the opportunities of the future generations. It is a

process in which the exploitation of resources, the technological developments and the transformation of the society are all in coherence with present and future generation which contains a potential of fulfilling the needs and aspirations of present and future.

Sustainable development is a complex and complicated mechanism which needs global attention and efforts to address a wide range of the issues and challenges including poverty, inequality, depletion of resources and environmental degradation.

The term "**indigenous knowledge**" (**IK**) describes the collective wisdom, techniques and skills that indigenous communities have amassed over many centuries and generations. Maintaining biodiversity, protecting natural resources and guaranteeing sustainable livelihoods, all depend heavily on this knowledge. But unfortunately the indigenous knowledge has been marginalized, sidelined due to modernization, industrialization, globalization and establishment of technological hubs putting its survival into danger.

The IK systems have played a crucial role in the sustainable development since centuries by promoting social cohesiveness, economic resilience and environmental preservation. The paper emphasizes the need to learn and retain from this preserved knowledge surviving through modernization, climate change and globalization which pose threats to this knowledge.

And also it suggests methods for preserving and incorporating it into the modern development frameworks. It is concluded that attaining long-term sustainability requires acknowledging and preserving ingrained indigenous knowledge; its importance in promoting social cohesiveness, economic resilience, environmental preservation and the contribution to the society leading to sustainable development is presented in this research paper. Innovative methods used in preserving the heritage are also discussed.

The contribution of the Indigenous Knowledge for the Sustainable Development is closely related in a number of ways such as:

Treasure of Ethnic Knowledge: Indigenous communities are not only familiar with the geographical regions, conditions and the ecosystem of the particular local areas, but also are well informed about the characteristics of the flora and fauna of their surroundings with which they derive the best survival techniques.

Environmental Conservation: To efficiently manage the natural resources, indigenous communities depend on their traditional ecological awareness. Crop rotation, agroforestry and controlled burning are some of the techniques that support the preservation of soil fertility and biodiversity.

Adaptation to the Climatic Changes: The ecosystems on which the indigenous communities dwell are based on traditional practices, customs and ethnic techniques which are endangered due to rising temperatures, deforestation and loss of biodiversity. Rainwater harvesting and traditional irrigation techniques are the examples of indigenous methods that have guided the modern society in adapting the sustainable methods to adjust the climatic variations and solve the problem of water shortage.

Health and Medicine: Herbal remedies and traditional healing methods support healthcare particularly in isolated locations where access to the contemporary medical services are limited. These health care methods use herbs, seeds, roots, trees' barks, sands, clay etc. and many other natural methods not only to cure the diseases but also to provide sustainable solutions to the patients for the better survival and ailment free lives.

The Holistic Approach: These communities believe in the inter-dependence and the inter-connectedness of all the living organisms including man, plants, animals and the environment for their mutual survival. They attach spiritual significance to the safety of the sacred nature and consider natural resources as the manifestation of God.

Cultural and Practical Knowledge: These people contribute valuably in the preservation of cultural and traditional knowledge through traditional customs, rituals, practices, belief systems passed on to the next generation verbally and are saved through folk lore, music, arts, language and spiritual wisdom.

Economic Sustainability: Indigenous craftsmanship, sustainable agriculture and ecofriendly tourism provide economic opportunities also while preserving the cultural heritage.

Cultural Connectivity and Social Bonding: Indigenous languages, storytelling methods, folklores, anecdotes, life experiences of the ancestors and rituals play a crucial role in maintaining the identity of the particular community providing the social stability and ethnic legacy.

The greatest proportion of the indigenous peoples is found in Asia and the Pacific region (70.5%), followed by Africa (16.3%), Latin America and the Caribbean (11.5%), Northern America (1.6%), and Europe and Central Asia (0.1%) as per the data collected by the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) in 2020. In order to improve communication with them and guarantee that policies uphold their rights, UNESCO has founded the International Indigenous Peoples' Forum on World Heritage in 2018.

LITERATURE REVIEW:-

The United Nations' Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples (UNDRIP)¹⁰ and the International Labor Organization's (ILO) 1989, Indigenous and Tribal Peoples Convention (No. 169) ⁹; both strongly recognize and regard the indigenous culture and implemented the primary international documents together outlining the rights of indigenous peoples. The UNDRIP is the most comprehensive statement of indigenous peoples' rights ever created, giving collective rights to the extent of prominence in international human rights law. It was adopted by the UN General Assembly in 2007 in response to the Commission on Human Rights appointing the UN Special Rapporteur on the rights of Indigenous Peoples in 2001. Nearly 60 indigenous languages have been translated under the UNDRIP. The intellectual property rights (IPR) of indigenous people are being catered for due to the efforts of UNDRIP.

Though it is lately realized that the preservation and protection of the indigenous communities are crucial for the sustainability but the concerned authorities still need to conserve, make strict rules and policies facilitating these communities to be in harmony with nature and remain untouched by the modernization and other threats.

OBJECTIVES:-

The main objective of this paper is to identify appropriate technologies for the preservation of Indigenous knowledge and also:

To know the challenges in the preservation of indigenous knowledge.

To discuss the strategies to be adopted to protect the indigenous knowledge system.

To present the Case Studies from various parts of India and other countries that showcase age old practices preserving indigenous knowledge and promoting sustainability, benefiting the current generations.

CHALLENGES IN THE PRESERVATION OF INDIGENOUS KNOWLEDGE

The Indigenous Communities are confronted by a number of issues which jeopardize their sustainability, customs and their way of lives. The risks, threats faced by them which endanger their survival are as follows:-

MODERNIZATION: The dominance of modern education and economic systems in vogue are causing the erosion of indigenous practices and values at a rapid speed.

CLIMATE CHANGE: The ever rising global temperatures, deforestation and loss of biodiversity threaten the ecosystems that indigenous communities rely upon.

LOSS OF THE INDIGENOUS LANGUAGES: Many indigenous languages face extinction and are at the verge of decline, due to which the knowledge embedded within the language is also lost. As many of these primitive languages face extinction, the knowledge ingrained and embedded in them also becomes irrecoverable.

CULTURAL EROSION: Indigenous languages, customs and traditions gradually disappear as a result of the predominance and influence of various cultures emerging from the mainstream and social media and with the introduction of the formal education in the tribal communities.

INSTITUTIONAL BARRIERS: Indigenous knowledge is constantly ignored by the intellectual property rights which encourage bio piracy and the exploitation of the tribal communities. Intellectual property laws fail to recognize and secure the indigenous knowledge systems and control the bio piracy and exploitation of the tribal knowledge.

LAND DISPOSITION: Indigenous people lose the access to their ancestral lands and resources due to unlawful encroachments on the pretext of building industries, developing agriculture, mining, building bridges, laying railway tracks, constructing high ways and due to the urban growth.

MARGINALISED AND UNRECOGNIZED POLITICAL REPRESENTATION: The Political representation of Indigenous voices are frequently excluded from the process of policy making depriving them of their fundamental rights of the governance that does not address their unique needs and requirements.

STRATEGIES TO BE ADOPTED TO CONSERVE THE INDIGENOUS COMMUNITIES:

The strategies to be followed for preserving the Indigenous Knowledge are..

INVOLVEMENT AND PARTICIPATION OF THE COMMUNITY MEMBERS:

Participation and involvement of the community members in the decision making process at the local government level will give them a voice in the planning and policy making, assuring them that their knowledge will be protected and respected.

INNOVATIVE METHODS FOR CONSERVING INDIGENOUS WISDOM INCLUDE...

DOCUMENTATION AND DIGITIZATION: Through documentation and digitization the knowledge preservation can be done by capturing the oral traditions, customs and the local wisdom in the form of digital archives

EDUCATION AND INTEGRATION: By integrating it in the regular education system and incorporating the indigenous knowledge into the school curricula and research institutions will open the doors for the development and research to foster the appreciation, application and the representation of the disappearing knowledge and communities.

LEGAL PROTECTION AND GOVERNMENT'S SUPPORT: Traditional knowledge can be kept from being exploited by bolstering intellectual property rights and granting legal recognition to it. Strengthening intellectual property rights and identifying the traditional knowledge legally can prevent its exploitation and misuse.

COLLABORATION WITH MODERN SCIENCE: Collaboration with modern science and technology will ensure the sustainability initiatives in the fields of environmental conservation, agricultural practices and medicine. The sustainability can be strengthened by combining the scientific research with indigenous knowledge.

CASE STUDIES ON INDIGENOUS KNOWLEDGE AND SUSTAINABILITY

Several successful approaches have been demonstrating the effective application of indigenous knowledge across the various countries as well as in India. Some of the traditional conservation techniques like katta, sand bores, johads, bawdi, bamboo drip irrigation systems are good examples of water conservation practices in India.

Ziro Valley Agriculture in the State of Arunachal Pradesh is an example from **India** which represents the practice of sustainability. The Apatani tribe in Arunachal Pradesh has been successfully practicing the sustainable wet-rice farming with an extensive network of irrigation channels along with the fish cultivation to preserve the biodiversity and maintain the soil fertility. The agriculture in Ziro Valley includes rice farming, fish farming, cultivation of millets and agroforestry. The farmers of Apatani Valley practice subsistence agriculture and fishing.

The Ziro valley was nominated for shortlisting in the UNESCO World Heritage Site in 2002. It is known for the Apatanis' sustainable lifestyle for the paddy cultivation and fish farming which had been evolved due to the requirement and need to make the optimal use of the land and water resources. The need arose when they migrated to the water-scarce valley long ago. Even now the Apatanis continue to use all the organic household and livestock waste, ash from the burnt rice stalks and decomposed weeds to cure their terraced farms, which holds nearly 10 cm of water. And for fish farming they adopt the most appropriate and right time to release common carp [fish] hatchlings in the fields to produce 200- 400 kg fish per hectare per season.

But the challenges of urbanization started to appear as the Apatani people's traditional lifestyle is changing. They are moving to the cities from the valley for work due to which the agricultural land is shrinking. Farmers prefer small tractors nowadays instead of traditional ploughs which may cause damage the fragile ecology.

Sacred Groves of India: Some examples of the sustained practices from the Indian states of Rajasthan, Kerala and Maharashtra where the local communities have preserved the patches of forests as the sacred groves protecting the biodiversity and ensuring the ecological balance are also presented here.

Sacred groves are the places of pilgrimage in many Indian religions. They are often associated with temples, monasteries, shrines and burial grounds. They are considered to be ecologically unique and biodiversity rich regions. They are home to many rare and endangered plants. Sacred groves are also found in the Western Ghats of Karnataka, Aravali Hills of Rajasthan, Khasi and Jaintia Hills of Meghalaya, Chanda and Bastar of Madhya Pradesh and Khecheopalri Lake of Sikkim.

These remarkable practices are the establishment and preservation of the local flora. These Groves are known as "Orans,"- [Rajasthan] and are considered sacred and protected by the local communities [Rathore and Shekhawat-2011]. They are hotspots of biodiversity accommodating a variety of plant and animal species. The trees and vegetation in these groves helps in moisture retention and soil conservation, contributing to water conservation efforts.

Water resource management plays a crucial role in the Thar Desert of Rajasthan. The severe scarcity of water is a major challenge in this region. The traditional management of water resources is essential to ensure the survival of both humans and the unique ecosystem of the desert (Machiwal et al., 2023). The main reason of water resource managements is important in the Thar Desert is for sustaining the agricultural practices. Farmers rely totally on the irrigation systems such as Jhalara and Kund to cultivate crops and sustain their livelihoods.

The traditional water harvesting techniques practiced since centuries in Rajasthan not only help collect and store rainwater but also ensure an un interrupted supply for agriculture. Besides maintaining a very well organized water resource management, it is also crucial for the survival of wildlife and plant species in the Thar Desert.

Sacred groves like the Kolu Pabuji, Oran exist as biodiversity hotspots and provide a sanctuary for the local vegetation and wild life. A well placed water management through structures like Bawadis, Tanka and Johad helps maintain the balance of the desert ecosystem and ensures the

availability of water for both humans and wildlife. An effective water resource management in the Thar Desert is crucial for mitigating the impacts of climate change. As climate patterns shift and rainfall becomes unpredictable, it becomes essential to conserve and manage water resources efficiently (Burark et al., 2023). Traditional water conservation structures such as Talab/Bandhi and Bhandar Pahad restore the groundwater and prevent water scarcity during dry seasons as it is vital for sustaining agriculture, preserving biodiversity and overcoming the challenges of climate change. Pushkar Traditional Water Management in Rajasthan is also an indigenous water harvesting systems possessing the step wells and johads which have been contributing greatly in conserving water since centuries in the arid regions. By adopting the traditional practices and introducing the innovative solutions, the government and the people can establish the long-term sustainability of water resources in this desert region.

Sacred Groves of Maharashtra are called Devrai or Devrahati in the west and Devgudi by the Madiya tribal in the east. They are found in tribal and non-tribal areas and protected from all the human interference on the grounds of religious rituals and rites. Tribes believe that some of these plants are homes of Gods and Goddesses. There are about 2820 sacred groves which have been documented in Maharashtra. These groves are dedicated to the dieties called Maruti, Vaghoba, Vira, Bhiroba, Khandoba and Shirikai.

Sacred Groves of Kerala are the forests that are protected for their biodiversity and cultural significance. They are home to many plants, animals and water bodies and are traditionally called as Kāvû across the Malabar Coast in Kerala, South India. The sacred groves in the Western Ghats are a rich source of fruit bearing trees and small water bodies and act as habitat for several species of birds and reptiles.

Every village in Kerala has a temple which was invariably associated with a Kavuvu (sacred grove) and that Kavuvu used to be distinct and unique in its biological diversity. People were not allowed to enter the Kavuvus except for worship. It is estimated that Kerala has about 1500 big and small Kavuvus. A survey conducted by the Rajiv Gandhi Tropical Botanical Garden and Research Institute, Thiruvananthapuram identified 261 Kavuvus in Kerala. In spite of the urbanization and developmental processes, the northern districts of Kerala have managed to conserve many sacred groves.

These sacred groves support a diverse bird life. Several Studies show that a good number of species remained protected over the decades in these groves. In a study conducted by P. O. Nameer, Professor and Head, Centre for Wildlife Studies, College of Forestry of the Kerala

Agricultural University (KAU) and K.M. Jyothi of KAU studied 15 major sacred groves of Kannur and Kasaragod districts in 2015. They observed and found that about 107 bird species belonging to the 48 families and 17 orders were thriving there, among which 17 species were migratory birds.

Another study done by Nameer Sashikumar identified four species of native birds including grey headed bulbul and small sun bird-[2004] in the sacred groves of north Kerala. This study had recognized 129 species of birds existing in 15 sacred groves.

Some of the other examples of the sustainable actions and traditional wisdom applied to protect the indigenous knowledge in the other places of the world are...

Amazon Rainforest of Brazil: Indigenous land management practices in Brazil have proven to be crucial in conserving the biodiversity and preventing deforestation.

Maasai Pastoralism of Kenya and Tanzania: The traditional livestock management techniques have helped Maasai of Kenya in sustaining the rangelands despite climatic diversity.

Indigenous Rice Farming in Philippines: Traditional rice farming methods have contributed greatly in providing the food security to the people and maintaining the environmental sustainability.

INNOVATIVE METHODS FOR CONSERVING INDIGENOUS WISDOM INCLUDE...

The development of sustainable technologies to meet the demands is the main goal of appropriate technologies being developed for the safety of Indigenous communities. They concentrate on developing technologies suitable for them. This wisdom serve as the foundation for their technological advancement. Large collections of items with cultural or historical significance to Indigenous peoples can be found in many museums, archives, libraries, and other cultural organizations around the world.

DOCUMENTATION AND DIGITIZATION: Through documentation and digitization the knowledge preservation can be done by capturing the oral traditions, customs and the local wisdom in the form of digital archives. This is being provided by new, innovative, high-quality 2D and 3D scanners, collaborative interactive software tools, high-speed networks and emerging grid technologies that facilitate communication and the sharing of resources and knowledge between geographically dispersed groups.

EDUCATION AND INTEGRATION: By integrating it in the regular education system and incorporating the indigenous knowledge into the school curricula and research institutions will

open the doors for the development and research to foster the appreciation, application and the representation of the disappearing knowledge and communities.

In developed countries the indigenous communities are using technologies including Internet-based radio broadcasting, document digitization and videoconferencing. Most of these technologies are employed to support and maintain indigenous history, culture and human rights campaigning.

LEGAL PROTECTION AND GOVERNMENT'S SUPPORT: Traditional knowledge can be kept from being exploited by bolstering intellectual property rights and granting legal recognition to it. Strengthening intellectual property rights and identifying the traditional knowledge legally can prevent its exploitation and misuse. The community must be involved in "the process of formation and diffusion of their knowledge" and information must be kept for the community's own benefit.

COLLABORATION WITH MODERN SCIENCE: Collaboration with modern science and technology will ensure the sustainability initiatives in the fields of environmental conservation, agricultural practices and medicine. The sustainability can be strengthened by combining the scientific research with indigenous knowledge.

MUSEUMS: The rich cultural legacy of our world is preserved in large part by museums, archives and with anthropologists. These organizations contribute to a wider appreciation and respect for other cultures by documenting and disseminating the music, arts, knowledge and customs of indigenous populations. The ethnographic collections of museums and other organizations contain priceless, even unique, documents of long-gone customs, extinct languages and local histories that are essential for the identity of indigenous people.

THE USE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY: Indigenous peoples currently use technologies including online radio broadcasting, document digitization and video conferencing. Most of these technologies are employed to support and maintain their history, culture and human rights. Advanced groups use the Internet for video conferencing, chat rooms, radio stations, email and gathering information through web browsing.

Presently there are many communities using the technology including educational initiatives that support and cater to their technological requirements. Other institutions collaborate with indigenous communities to build collecting centers, while some other which have indigenous materials are helping to make these things available to them.

SOCIAL MEDIA TECHNOLOGY: Social media tools can produce user-generated content and shared it with the communities . East African social and geographic communities as well as broader audiences get benefit from the creation, access and sharing of knowledge and skills through social media platforms like YouTube, Facebook, Google Docs, and Twitter.

CONCLUSION:-

Indigenous knowledge system is a valuable asset for the sustainable development which offers solutions to the contemporary environmental and socio-economic challenges. The preservation and protection requires a multi-faceted approach of education, legal protection, community participation and integration with modern science. The various examples mentioned above regarding cultivation methods, water management for safeguarding flora and fauna with the traditional practices, water conservation in the Thar Desert and in the other drought prone places of India and other countries have proven to be effective in addressing water scarcity besides respecting the cultural heritage and preserving the biodiversity of the region

It is very important to study and conduct research, document and promote these practices to secure a sustainable future for the affected regions and its inhabitants. People should be made aware about the necessity of the conservation to make a positive impact on the environment and the lives of the people and communities. The exploration of traditional practices in water conservation in the Thar Desert of Rajasthan reveals the invaluable wisdom of the local communities in harmonizing with their arid environment. These practices, deeply rooted in their cultural heritage have proven to be effective in alleviating water scarcity and preserving the balance of the ecosystem. Adapting the indigenous knowledge will not only benefit indigenous communities but also contribute and give a direction to the efforts of global sustainability. The collaborative strategies of the governments, researchers, developers and planners shall ensure that this vital knowledge is restored and guarded for the future generations.

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